

Kasr tartibli differensial operator ishtirok etgan integro-differensial tenglamalar uchun integral shartli masalalar

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada kasr tartibli differensial operator qatnashgan integro-differensial tenglama uchun ikkinchi tur integral shartli masala o‘rganilgan.

1-masala.

$$y''(x) + p_1(x)y'(x) + p_2(x)y(x) + p_3(x)D_{ax}^\alpha \omega(x)y(x) = f(x),$$

$$x \in (a, b)$$

(1)

tenglamaning $[a, b]$ segmentda aniqlangan, uzluksiz va

$$y(a) = k_1, \quad y'(b) + hy(b) = h \int_a^\beta y(t) dt + k_2 \quad (2)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi topilsin, bu yerda $k_1, k_2, h, \alpha, \beta$ -berilgan sonlar bo‘lib, $a \leq \alpha < \beta \leq b$.

(2) dan ko‘rinib turibdiki $h = 0$ da 1-masaladan

$$y(a) = k_1 \quad y'(b) = k_2 \quad (3)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi masala kelib chiqadi. Agar

$0 < |h| \leq 1$ va $a < \alpha < \beta < b$ bo‘lsa, (2) shartlarning ikkinchisini undagi

integralga o‘rta qiymat haqidagi teoremani tatbiq qilib, $y'(b) + hy(\xi) = k_2$

ko‘rinishda yozib olish mumkin bo‘ladi, bu yerda $\xi \in [a, b]$ segmentdagi

qandaydir tayinlangan son. Demak, bu holda, 1-masala

$$y(a) = k_1, \quad y'(b) + hy(\xi) = k_2 \quad (4)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi topilganidek o‘rganiladi. $0 < |q| < 1$ va

$[\alpha, \beta] = [a, b]$ bo‘lgan holda ham 1-masala 4-shartga keltirib, o‘rganiladi.

Yuqoridagilarni e'tiborga olgan holda 1-masalani $h = 1$, $\alpha = a$, $\beta = b$ bo'lgan holda, ya'ni (2) shartlar

$$y(a) = k_1 \quad y'(b) + y(b) = \int_a^b y(t) dt + k_2 \quad (5)$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'lgan holda o'rganamiz.

Bu masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagonaligini ko'rsatish uchun xuddi 3-shartdagi kabi, (1) tenglamani $[a, x]$ oraliqda ikki marta integrallab,

$$y'(x) + p_1(x)y(x) + \int_a^x \left\{ p_2(t) - p_1'(t) + \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \left[p_3(x)(x-t)^{-\alpha} - \int_t^x p_3'(z)(z-t)^{-\alpha} dz \right] \right\} y(t) dt = \int_a^x f(t) dt + y'(a) + k_1 p_1(a), \quad (6)$$

va

$$y(x) + \int_a^x \left\{ p_1(t) + [p_2(t) - p_1'(t)](x-t) + \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_t^x (\xi-t)^{-\alpha} [p_3(\xi) - p_3'(\xi)(x-\xi)] d\xi \right\} y(t) dt = \int_a^x (x-t) f(t) dt + y'(a)(x-a) + k_1 p_1(a)(x-a) + k_1 \quad (7)$$

tengliklarga ega bo'lamiz. (6) va (7) tengliklarni quyidagicha yozib olamiz;

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$$\begin{aligned}
 y(x) = & -\int_a^x \left\{ p_1(t) + [p_2(t) - p_1'(t)](x-t) + \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_t^x (\xi-t)^{-\alpha} [p_3(\xi) - p_3'(\xi)(x-\xi)] y(t) dt \right\} + \\
 & + \int_a^x (x-t) f(t) dt + y'(a)(x-a) + k_1 p_1(a)(x-a) + k_1, \\
 y'(x) = & -p_1(x) y(x) - \int_a^x \left\{ p_2(t) - p_1'(t) + \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [p_3(x)(x-t)^{-\alpha} - \right. \\
 & \left. - \int_t^x p_3'(z)(z-t)^{-\alpha} dz \right\} y(t) dt + \int_a^x f(t) dt + y'(a) + k_1 p_1(a).
 \end{aligned}$$

Bulardan quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$y(x) = \int_a^x K_2(x,t) y(t) dt + f_2(x) + y'(a)(x-a),$$

(8)

$$y'(x) = -p_1(x) y(x) - \int_a^x K_1(x,t) y(t) dt + f_1(x) + y'(a),$$

(9)

bu yerda

$$f_1(x) = \int_a^x f(t) dt + k_1 p_1(a), \quad f_2(x) = \int_a^x (x-t) f(t) dt + k_1 p_1(a)(x-a) + k_1,$$

$$K_1(x,t) = p_1(t) + [p_2(t) - p_1'(t)](x-t) +$$

$$+ \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_t^x (\xi-t)^{-\alpha} [p_3(\xi) - p_3'(\xi)(x-\xi)] d\xi,$$

$$K_2(x,t) = -p_1(t) + [p_2(t) - p_1'(t)](x-t) -$$

$$- \frac{\omega(t)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_t^x (\xi-t)^{-\alpha} [p_3(\xi) - p_3'(\xi)(x-\xi)].$$

$K_1(x, t)$, $K_2(x, t) - \{(x, t) : a \leq x \leq b\}$ to'rtburchakda chegaralangan va bo'lakli uzluksiz bo'lgan ma'lum funksiyalar, $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ esa $[a, b]$ da uzluksiz ma'lum funksiyalar.

(8) dan quyidagini topamiz:

$$\int_a^b y(t) dt = \int_a^b \int_a^b K_2(x, t) y(t) dt + \int_a^b f_2(t) dt + \frac{1}{2} y'(a)(b-a)^2.$$

Buni va

(8) va (9) tengliklarda $x=b$ deb,

$$y'(b) = -p_1(b)y(b) - \int_a^b K_1(b, t) y(t) dt + f_1(b) + y'(a),$$

(10)

$$y(b) = \int_a^b K_2(b, t) y(t) dt + f_2(b) + y'(a)(b-a),$$

(11)

tengliklarni topamiz. (10) va (11) ni (5) shartga qo'yib,

$$\begin{aligned} & y'(a) \cdot \{(b-a)[-p_1(b)+1]+1\} = \\ & = -[-p_1(b)+1] \cdot \int_a^b K_2(b, t) y(t) dt + \int_a^b K_1(b, t) y(t) dt - \\ & - f_2(b)[-p_1(b)+1] - f_1(b) + \int_a^b y(t) dt + k_2 \end{aligned}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Agar $(b-a)[-p_1(b)+1]+1 \neq 0$ bo'lsa $y'(a)$ oxirgi tenglikdan bir qiymatli topiladi

$$y'(a) = \left\{ -[-p_1(b)+1] \cdot \int_a^b K_2(b, t) y(t) dt + \int_a^b K_1(b, t) y(t) dt - \right. \\ \left. - f_2(b)[-p_1(b)+1] - f_1(b) + \int_a^b y(t) dt + k_2 \right\} \cdot \frac{1}{(b-a)[-p_1(b)+1]+1}.$$

Uni (8) ga qo'yib,

$$y(x) = \int_a^x K_2(x,t)y(t)dt + f_2(x) + \left\{ -[-p_1(b)+1] \cdot \int_a^b K_2(b,t)y(t)dt + \int_a^b K_1(b,t)y(t)dt - \right. \\ \left. -f_2(b)[-p_1(b)+1] - f_1(b) + \int_a^b y(t)dt + k_2 \right\} \cdot \frac{x-a}{(b-a)[-p_1(b)+1]+1}$$

(12) $y(x)$ ga nisbatan ikkinchi tur Fredgolm integral tenglamasiga ega bo‘lamiz.

Agar berilganlarga qo‘yilgan $f(x) \in C[a,b]$, $p_1(x) \in C^1[a,b]$, $p_2(x), p_3(x) \in C^2[a,b]$ shartlarda $|K_2(x,t)| < 1$ bo‘lsa, (12) tenglama va, demak, 1-masala yagona yechimga ega bo‘ladi.

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